

Chemoselective acylation of amines, thiols and phenols using 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT) as a new and effective reagent under mild condition

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Abstract : A facile chemoselective acylation of amines, thiols and phenols using 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT) under mild condition is described. New reagent, high product yield, short reaction time, ease of operation and solvent free reaction condition is the most acceptable feature of the present method.

Keywords : Thiol, phenol, amine, acylation, chemoselective.

Introduction

The acylation of amines, thiols and phenols is most common and often used as a protecting group in organic synthesis. It provides an efficient and inexpensive mean in the multistep synthetic process^{1,2}. Acetic anhydride and acetyl chloride are generally used in presence of acid³ or base⁴ catalysts in organic medium. Some of these reagents and catalysts led to waste as well as some reactions involving toxic organic solvents. Lewis acids such as MgBr₂⁵, ZnCl₂⁶, CoCl₂⁷, TaCl₅⁸, InCl₃⁹, ZrCl₄¹⁰, RuCl₃¹¹, BiCl₃¹², ZrOCl₂.8H₂O¹³, TiO₂/SO₄²⁻¹⁴ were used. Recently acylation is carried out using metal triflates¹⁵,

perchlorates¹⁶, supported reagents like HBF₄-SiO₂¹⁷, HClO₄-SiO₂¹⁸, KF-Al₂O₃¹⁹, Nafion-H²⁰, Ytria-zirconia²¹, Clay²², Zeolite-HSZ-360²³, iodine²⁵, oxime ester^{26a}, H-beta zeolite^{26b} and *Pseudomonas capsia ps-lipase* absorbed on celite²⁷ have been reported.

However inspite of their potential utility, many of these methods suffer from drawbacks such as long reaction time, use of expensive reagents, incompatibility of other functional group and relatively drastic reactions conditions. Therefore, mild efficient and metal free reactions would extend the scope of acylation process.

Scheme 2

Results and discussion

In recent years, carrying out reactions without solvent is necessary in order to make the synthetic method more efficient. These observations led us to search for the method of improved chemoselectivity, yield and purity of the products. The present method describes a clean, solvent free acylation of amine, thiol and phenols by using new and efficient acylating reagent 2,4,6-triacetyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT) (A).

We have synthesized various *N*-acylamines with diverse functionalities via novel acylating agent A with amines. In addition, we have examined the possibilities of these reactions for selective amidation of amino alcohols (Scheme 3).

During the course, we have observed that aliphatic amines such as ethanolamine, morpholine, piperidine and *N*-methyl piperazine (Table 1; entry 3t-v) underwent smooth acylation to afford corresponding *N*-acylated products at room temperature. In order to study the higher reactivity of aliphatic amines, we have performed the acylation by treating the mixture of *p*-toluidine and ethanolamine with present acylating agent (Scheme 3). It was observed that the acylation of aliphatic amine undergo fast acylation to afford *N*-acetyl ethanolamine in 78% yield. Whereas, only 30% 4-methyl acetanilide was isolated as the acylation product of *p*-toluidine (Scheme 3).

Encouraged by these results we have conducted the acylation of mixture of aniline, phenol and thiophenol using A and reaction conditions. But acetanilide was the only product isolated (90%) at the end rather than acylated phenol or thiophenol. Hence the methodology presented here has excellent chemoselectivity for amines (Scheme 4).

It has been found that at 80 °C temperature phenols and thiols undergo acylation to afford corresponding acylated products in good yields (Table 1, entry 3l-q). An aliphatic alcohol does not undergo acylation in the course of reaction (Table 1, entry 3k, 3w) even after 20 h. It has been observed that nature of the substituent on amines does not show satisfactory effect on the acylation process. Effect of substituents plays an important role in the acylation process of phenols and thiol. Phenols and thiophenol possessing electron donating substituents undergo slow acylation process with low product yield (Table 1, entry 3m, 3o). Therefore, reaction was found to be general for all aliphatic and aromatic amines only and not for phenols and thiols.

The novel acylating reagent 2,4,6-triacetyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT) was prepared by the reaction of 2,4,6-trichlorotriazine and acetic acid in dichloromethane using triethyl amine. A white suspension of salt was formed. Further, after the addition of acetic acid in dichloromethane and stirring for 3 h, reaction mixture was filtered and

Scheme 3

Note

Scheme 4

Table 1. Acylation of amines, thiols and phenols using 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT) under solvent free condition

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^{b, c}
3a	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NHCOCH ₃	10	90 [Ref. 7, 9]
3b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	92 [Ref. 9, 11, 26]
3c	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	5	98 [Ref. 9, 11, 26]
3d	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	77
3e	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	80
3f	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	89 [Ref. 9, 13]
3g	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	92
3h	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	74 [Ref. 2b]
3i	3-MeC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	3-MeC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	5	95
3j	NH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂	CH ₃ CONHCH ₂ CH ₂ NHCOCH ₃	5	>99
3k	NH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	HOCH ₂ CH ₂ NHCOCH ₃	5	>99
3l	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ OH	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ OCOCH ₃	20 ^a	79
3m	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ OH	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ OCOCH ₃	20 ^a	65 [Ref. 9, 13]
3n	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ OH	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ OCOCH ₃	20 ^a	72
3o	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ SH	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ SCOCH ₃	20 ^a	58
3p	C ₆ H ₅ SH	C ₆ H ₅ SCOCH ₃	20 ^a	76
3q	4-HOOC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-HOOC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	66
3r	4-HOC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	4-HOC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	10	82
3s	4,4'-di-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ CONHC ₆ H ₄ NHCOCH ₃	20	55 [Ref. 13]
3t			5	>99
3u			5	>99
3v			5	>99
3w	HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	No reaction	20 h	-

^aAcylation at 80 °C temperature. ^bYield of pure isolated products.

^cProducts were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analysis and by comparison with authentic samples.

solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford a white crystalline 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (TAT).

In the typical experimental procedure for acylation of *p*-toluidine, TAT (1 mmol) was grinded with *p*-toluidine (3 mmol) at room temperature for 5 min. The progress of reaction can be judged using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) using petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (4.5 : 0.5 ml)

solvent system. After completion of reaction, reaction mixture was poured in saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (5 ml) to afford white crystalline *p*-methyl acetanilide. The product was further collected by filtration and purification was done by recrystallization in ethanol. The confirmation and purity of the formed product was checked by spectral analysis. The IR (KBr) spectrum of

3c shows characteristic absorption at ν 1665, 1600 cm^{-1} due to -CO-N; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS, δ ppm) of **3c** shows singlet with δ 2.13 for Ar- CH_3 protons, singlet with δ 2.32 for -CO- CH_3 protons and characteristic broad singlet at δ 5.9 for -CO-NH proton. Mass spectrum also confirmed the structure **3c** with M^+ 149.4 (M.F. = $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$, M.W. = 149).

Experimental

All the chemicals were used of analytical grade. The acylated products were characterized by using IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectra. The progress of reaction was checked by using TLC technique using petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (4.5 : 0.5 ml). The purity of resultant compound was judged by IR and ^1H NMR. The melting points were determined on the open capillary tube and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Bomem FT-IR MB-104 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AC-300 MHz in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal standard.

General procedure for the acylation of amines :

The mixture of 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (1 mmol), amine (3 mmol) was grinded under solvent free condition at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ for specified time. After completion of reaction (TLC), reaction mixture was mixed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (10 ml). Further *N*-acylated products were collected by filtration and recrystallization was done by using proper solvents.

General procedure for the acylation of thiols and phenols :

The mixture of 2,4,6-triacyloxy-1,3,5-triazine (1 mmol), phenol or thiol (3 mmol) was grinded under solvent free condition at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ temperature to afford the desired acylated thiols and phenols in good yield (Table 1).

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